

Electrophoretic Studies of some Quercetin Glycosides

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The identification and separation of flavonoid compounds from a mixture presents considerable interest in several fields. Electrophoretic migration studies of flavonoid compounds have been reported earlier and identification of flavonoid bisulphates and the distinction of glucuronides from glucosides have been made¹. The present communication compares the electrochromatographic behaviour of five quercetin glycosides with that of aglycone : quercetin (1), quercetin-3-*O*-rhamnoglucoside (2), quercetin-3-*O*-galactoside (3), quercetin-3-*O*-glucorhamnoarabinoside (4), quercetin-3-*O*-glucoside (5) and quercetin-3-*O*-dirhamnoside (6).

- 1; R' = H
- 2; R' = Rhaglu
- 3, R' = Gal
- 4; R' = Glucorhamnoarabinoside
- 5; R' = Glucoside
- 6; R' = Dirhamnoside

Results and Discussion

The rate of electrophoretic mobility data at differ-

ent pH values for the compounds are given in Tables 1 and 2. From the direction of movement it is clear that at lower pH values, the mobility is due to the protonated species and at higher pH values the mobility is due to the deprotonated species. The difference in rate of movement of quercetin glycosides in various background electrolytes is in consideration with polarity of the compounds. The observed order of the rate of movement is as follows : trioside > dioside > monoside > aglycone. It is also observed that the difference in mobility of the quercetin glycosides is maximum at 2% boric acid and hence binary separation was carried out successfully with this background electrolyte. The mobility towards anode is due to the formation of boron complex².

Experimental

Electrophoresis was carried out in a Systronics 604 horizontal apparatus. All background electrolytes were prepared in conductivity water with A.R. grade chemicals. Whatman No. 1 chromatography paper (30 × 1 cm) was used as support strip. Three sets of buffer solutions were used as background electrolytes : Buffer set I–Britton-Robinson buffer (pH 2–12); Buffer set II– (i) CH₃COOH + HCOOH + H₂O (pH 2), (ii) 0.1M succinic acid (pH 2.7), (iii) 0.1M ammonium ox-

TABLE 1—RATE OF MOVEMENT (mm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹ × 10⁻⁶) OF QUERCETIN GLYCOSIDES IN

Compd. no.	Buffer Set I						Buffer Set II						Buffer Set III					
	pH 2.1	4	6	8	10	12	2	2.7	5.7	7.9	11	11.9	2	4	5	6	8	10
1	0	0	0	0	+2.08	+4.86	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	+1.34
2	-4.17	-4.17	-1.04	-0.69	+11.6	+14.58	-2.78	+1.5	+1.04	+1.04	+7.29	+7.98	-4.71	-3.47	-1.39	-0.69	+1.39	+5.55
3	-2.08	-2.08	-1.04	+0.35	+5.55	+9.72	-2.08	-1.39	0	+0.35	+2.78	+2.78	-2.08	-1.39	-0.69	-0.35	+0.69	+4.17
4	-5.9	-5.0	-0.69	-2.43	+13.89	+18.05	-4.17	0	+2.43	+2.43	+8.33	+9.0	-4.86	-4.86	0	+0.69	+2.78	+6.94
5	-1.04	-1.04	0	0	+2.08	+2.78	-1.39	0	0	0	0	+0.35	0	0	0	0	0	+2.08
6	-3.47	-3.47	-1.04	+0.69	+8.33	+13.89	-2.78	0	+0.69	+1.04	+7.29	+7.98	-4.86	-4.17	-1.39	-0.69	+1.39	+6.24

TABLE 2-RATE OF MOVEMENT ($\text{mm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1} \times 10^{-6}$) OF QUERCETIN GLYCOSIDES IN

Compd. no.	Boric acid			Borax solution		
	1%	2%	3%	1%	2%	3%
1	0	+0.69	+1.39	+7.98	+9.03	+4.86
2	+0.69	+5.55	+4.17	+7.29	+8.33	+4.17
3	0	+6.94	+4.16	+6.59	+7.64	+3.47
4	+4.86	+12.85	+12.15	+9.5	+10.42	+5.56
5	+1.04	+3.13	+3.47	+5.9	+6.25	+3.81
6	+2.78	+10.42	+9.02	+8.33	+9.37	+5.56

alate (pH 5.7), (iv) 0.1M diammonium hydrogen phthalate (pH 7.9), (v) 0.01M sodium carbonate (pH 11), (vi) 0.01M trisodium phosphate (pH 11.9); Buffer set III-(i) 0.05M HCl + 0.09M KCl (pH 2), (ii) potassium hydrogen phthalate (pH 4), (iii) EDTA disodium salt (pH 5), (iv) 0.01M CH_3COOH + 0.1M CH_3COONa (pH 6), (v) 0.1M NH_4OH + 0.1M NH_4Cl (pH 8), (vi) 0.1M NH_4OH + 0.1M NH_4OH (pH 10); 1, 2 and 3% boric acid and 1, 2 and 3% borax were also used as background electrolytes.

Clean and dried horizontal tank compartments were filled with equal volumes of aqueous background electrolyte and electrophoresis was carried out at a poten-

tial difference of 200 V/cm for 2 h. Electrochromatograms were viewed under ultraviolet light (366 nm) after exposure to ammonia vapour. The distance of migration was noted by measuring the length from the point of application to the middle of the zone. Migration towards cathode in an electric field is represented by negative sign and towards anode by positive sign.

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